

How Musical Is Living?

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Abstract. Eurological music makers and thinkers around the world are slowly coming to new terms with the age-old insight that music is not solely an aesthetic object—and that it is, rather, a complex activity that connects communities, beliefs, actions and knowledge about the world in ever-changing constellations. This happens at the same historical moment when the eurocentric mode of world domination, extraction and exploitation seems to have peaked and is assailed by self-doubt, battered by economic and climate crises which severely weaken its credibility and thus its ability to define how to live on this planet. Other voices emerge, new perspectives, hopes and models gain currency: one of them, I believe, is somehow related to the fact that all humans make music. But how can musicking around the world articulate a voice, play a role in these crises of living on a planet we continue to damage. How musical can the Anthropocene be?

In this universe, not all the musics are of our own making.

Ihab Hassan

I

Berlin, Mid-August 2020. A public performance in corona times, in an expansive, high, light and airy museum space in the Martin-Gropius-Bau. Installed each on separate locations throughout three large halls, 11 musicians over three full days from 10 am to 7 pm performed musical rituals with each other, recited poetic texts about how temporal processes had shaped their instruments, and explored how they could play with each other not only at a physical distance, but also in different tempi: each of them had to perform their improvisation score in different, continually changing metronome settings, entering and leaving the ritual at different times. Thus, in a purely organizational sense, they were never together, at most could they, only occasionally, find each other in moments of unforeseeable harmony – and yet they still somehow played and sang in a common spacetime of musical togetherness, as if they all had plugged in to a multilayered stream of music which appeared whenever their sounds met. Roland Barthes once coined the term “Idiorrhythmia”¹ for this kind of hetero-temporal behaviour which he observed in the communal life of certain monasteries. Thus, if I had to choose a formal term to describe the resulting musical texture, I would have to call it “idiorrhythmic heterophony.”

1. Roland Barthes, *Comment vivre ensemble: simulations romanesques de quelques espaces quotidiens*, Editions du Seuil / IMEC, Paris 2002.

The title of the performance, "...how to inhabit these different temporalities..."², reflected Barthes' concept. However, far from a How-To indicating some kind of music-demonstration, this performance was an experiment with an open question: What can musicking mean under the conditions of a global climate crisis, under the conditions of a pandemic – and under the conditions of an aesthetic crisis which probably is a collateral of the other two?

I had devised this performance as a conscious aesthetic response to our time, when both culture, in the form of audiovisual technology, and nature, in form of an insidiously destructive virus, force us to rethink the globally dominant mode of musicking, namely the live concert in front of a paying audience. It seems more than a coincidence that the word "viral" is used to describe both reasons why people may not anymore want to sit together crammed in a closed room next to hundreds of strangers – convenience and fear.

Three years ago, a conversation with one of my composition students, Nicholas Ryan, had alerted me to this, long before Corona. Nick was then in his last year as an undergraduate student in my composition class. Most of the students in this class tend to come from either pop/rock/jazz or electroacoustic/electonica music backgrounds. But Nick fully embraced the eurological 20th century avantgarde tradition. His student compositions were sparkling, intelligent and well-crafted de- and re-constructions of pieces by Ligeti, Tenney, Ablinger etc. in the spirit of YouTube mashups, exploring the limits of the computer as a live instrument in totally unexpected ways.

Each fall term, I use³ to take all my undergraduate composition students to the opening concert of the Montréal Contemporary Music season. For many of the first-year students, especially those from rural Canada, this may well be their first live encounter with eurological "classical" concert music. Afterwards, they must write a concert review from their point of view, their first grade of the term.

Nick told me that he had found the concert situation very difficult. He told me that he had never been to a concert "where I have to sit and listen. I usually seriously listen to all music in my own room, with headphones on. Sitting exposed in a hall with people breathing all around me made me very nervous and I could not focus on listening any more." He had never gone to a live concert to listen to music, and instead of this experience being a revelation to him (as we proponents of live musicking probably would like to believe) it was a shock...because people around him *breathed*.⁴ A few years later, many of us may suddenly understand his concern...

2. This installation performance by *Ensemble Extrakte Berlin* was part of the exhibition "Down To Earth" at the Martin Gropius Bau Berlin, curated by Tino Sehgal, Thomas Oberender and Anja Predeick, and part of the Berliner Festspiele's ongoing "Immersion" series since 2016.

3. Or better now: used...

4. It was only later that I remembered that Johannes Brahms, too, reportedly preferred lying on his sofa and reading a score to the social mingling of the concert.

Among the many things that we have started to re-examine in musical life, the form and event of the concert is one of the most far-reaching. Next to the engagement with questions of gender representation and a much too slowly increasing awareness of the systemic coloniality inherent in eurological musical praxis, questions of music making, music presentation and music performance have advanced from being arcane aesthetic concerns of academics and composers to a live-wire global issue. An architect friend who works in a Montréal office specializing in concert halls has told me that long-planned concert hall projects in Asia and the Americas are currently being put on hold: the architects are asked to devise cultural venues that would be corona-proof – and that request usually includes more flexible spaces that can be configured for alternate forms of music performance and presentation.

II

On the other hand, both viral events – the pandemic on the one hand, and the explosivity and ephemerality of pop on the other – are not as far reaching as they make themselves out to be. Most of you will be aware of how many music traditions present music in very different settings. Circumstances in which music plays an important role may diverge widely from the sit-still-and-listen concert – and a number of these traditional performance and presentation settings would actually be pandemic-proof. For traditions that were forced into the concert format by commercial considerations and by the colonial cultural hegemony of the West, a return to their previous forms of music presentation might actually be a relief. Whether it is one they want to adopt, is an open question.

Each temporality and each cultural economy has its own laws and its own constraints, much as it opens up particular opportunities and affordances. But – when we want to change the format of how we present something, what must we change in the sonic matter that we want to present?

The concert-installation by *Ensemble Extrakte* was thus just one of many test-runs for new ideas around the presentation and conception of music that are currently being undertaken around the globe. In devising it, it turned out to be very helpful that the music we make as an ensemble is not primarily eurological in nature.

“How to inhabit these different temporalities” was, in fact, the embodiment of what a few years ago would have been called a “glocal” work of art. Because culture tourism has virtually evaporated over the last months, most of the visitors were inhabitants of Berlin. The musicians, too, all live *in* Berlin, but neither they nor their instruments are *from* Berlin – they all once migrated to this city, from Korea (daegum), China (sheng, erhu, pipa), India (tabla, khayal), Bulgaria (different rural vocal styles), Syria (ud, riqq), Brandenburg (contemporary new music, duduk, blues harmonica), Bavaria (live electronics, turntables), Italy (double bass), Australia (oboe).

Each of the musicians is an accomplished artist in a different musical tradition, some learned, some oral, some professional, some folk, some rural, some urban underground. Seven years ago, when we first came together, we wanted to see what music could be like in a post-exotic globalized age where every larger city is inhabited by musicians and traditions from all around the globe. My question from the outset was: How could such different ways of performing music come together on a common path towards musicking. How would we be able to engage with each other's music and with potential audiences? How could we learn how to build a new practice of "musicking together"?

These are not trivial questions. In such an ensemble, every little detail of music making is under intense scrutiny. Do we tune together – or is tuning to a common frequency a false and ultimately colonialist homogenizing act? What is a rehearsal for: to learn a piece, to make a piece – or to learn trusting the other musicians, to spend time with them? Should we work towards a concert or just workshop our music, because our trans-traditional musicking "would never have the same quality and depth" as each musician's individual and intra-traditional music experiences?

But we also had purely musician-ly concerns: in a call-and-response progression, what kind of music counts as a response? Why did some of us hear something as an ornament, or a chord progression, while others hear the same notes as a melody? Are electronic instruments real music instruments? And, most crucially: How does one count time?

I remember a hetero-rhythmic concept for three percussionists, one Indian, one Arabian, one Korean, in which each musician would pursue their own cycles of differing lengths, but based on a common pulse, only to come together sometimes in a pleasant and ephemeral surprise. However, we never got this idea to work, it always ended in utter confusion and laughter. After many tries, when I offered to conduct, or clap the pulse throughout, we found out why: as each of the three pursued their own rhythmical cycles, they started to subtly but decisively modify the pulse. There seemed to be an elastic concept of time at work, which made them speed up or slow down as they anticipated the beginning of a new cycle.

Just as in harmony-based music we have the concept of a leading pitch, they had a sense of "leading time" – and each of them a different one, according to their own traditional references. It turned out to be especially problematic that their rubato around the start of some cycles depended not only on themselves, but on the tension they perceived in the pulsation of the others – and thus slight divergences quickly became amplified, mutated from phasing to counter-rhythm, until no-one knew any more what they were doing and where they all were. They each thought of rhythm not as a clockwork, but as a network of tensions – a concept which works well if all musicians share the same time flow, but not so well if their temporalities do not align. Rhythm and tempo, more than any other factor in music performance, depend on "reading the others and the room": and here, three master

percussionists at some point simply could not any more engage with the pulsating “room” they themselves had created for each other.

The question of being in time, always a source of friction and negotiation between musicians, became more than just a question of incompetence or ego: We could suddenly see it as a fundamental, structural problem between different music traditions. After one of our aborted attempts one of the musicians asked: “Say, even if we eventually manage to pull this together, will the audience know that we perform time in different ways? Will they not just hear it as one time-flow? How will *they* engage with our different times?”

III

“Performing,” “Engaging,” and “Knowing,” the three terms that set the agenda of this music symposium, all want to establish to different relationships of music to the world at large. When we perform, we implicitly assume that there are others to perform for or to. When we engage, we need someone or something to engage with. When we know, we want to know someone or something. All these would not be of particular interest if they were not uttered in the context of music making.

But in precisely this context, these terms put together become a challenge to the many arguments and received wisdoms all of us must have heard at some point in their musicking career:

Firstly: Is music really about **performing**? Granted, a lot of times it is, but do we not also know of many situations where music is just made to gratify the player: from the learned Qin player-philosopher who sits in a small hut far from any listener – to, again, Roland Barthes who discovered that Robert Schumann’s piano compositions provide much more meaningful experiences for those who play them than for those who just listen to them. That Schumann wrote true chamber music, best to be played alone at home.⁵

Secondly: Does music indeed have or foster an **engaged** relationship to mundane reality? Is it not overwhelmingly and across many different traditions seen as the very opposite – a sublime world of beauty that frees us from the trials and tribulations of mundane everyday life? And is not the music that explicitly does engage with the world – such as “politically engaged” music, or music for commercials or rituals – often one that many music lovers find a bit shallow and low-complexity?

Thirdly: Music is a polysemic art. Every musical process offers up a multitude of non-verbal, but potentially meaningful relations of elements within its sonic

5. Roland Barthes, Aimer Schumann, in: *L’obvie et l’obtus, Essais critiques III*, Editions du Seuil, Paris 1982.

matter. But the sonics of music by themselves do not offer any specific pointers to what it might mean to anyone or anything beyond this musical process.

This is precisely why music can lend intense, but unspecific emotion to almost any non-musical event – a fact well-known to film makers, religious leaders, politicians, political activists, sports fans, and advertising writers. Just add music to images, to words, to events, to rituals – and it will emotionally intensify whatever it is that these images, words, and rituals assert, even if we would never have guessed any of these assertions, had we just listened to the sonic stream alone.

And even the emotions that the sounds of music add to the mix are, as we all know, conventions established within traditions of listening. These emotions do not reside in the sonic matter of music, they are ascribed to it by its listeners, by societal convention or individual mythology.

So, what precisely do we mean when we speak of music as a means of knowing? What kind of knowledge can at all come from sounds lined up according to a musical convention, as almost all sounds are in the musics we know?

IV

I am sure that most of you, even while hearing this shopping list of received music wisdoms, started to formulate objections to them: that music is not about sonic matter alone but about the entire social and embodied context that brings it about: It's all about musicking, not about music, stupid! Or: that commercial or politically or ritually engaged music is anything but shallow, and that seeing these musical expressions as superficial is a prime example for e.g. white, liberal privilege. Or: that even those who play music only for themselves actually perform it for a projected Other – be it a divinity, a spiritual entity or the Divine, be it just inner truthfulness to an idealized version of the Self. And, finally, some of you may even have felt stirrings of ethnological exceptionalism: "All this may be true for most musicking, but it does really not apply to the particular group or scene I have studied."

This is the tension field which this symposium must navigate. The relationship of sound (and especially sound perceived as music) to the human and physical world is as tenuous and complex as the relationship of weather to physics – there undoubtedly is one, and through experience and study some phenomena seem to become predictable (i.e. understood and known): until the next freak event occurs that no one can explain.

Tim Ingold once suggested that we should talk about sound not in the spatial metaphors we usually employ (high sounds, low sounds, long notes, short notes etc.), because they evoke an inner image of a world of stable objects. Maybe sound and music should not be metaphorized as stable entities:

...the mundane term for what I have called the fluxes of the medium is weather. So long as we are... 'out in the open', the weather is no mere phantasm...It is, on the contrary, fundamental to perception. We do not perceive it, we perceive in it... In order to understand the phenomenon of sound...we should turn our attention skywards, to the realm of the birds, rather than towards the solid earth beneath our feet. The sky...is not a thing we see. It is rather luminosity itself. But it is sonority, too...perhaps our metaphors for describing auditory space should be derived not from landscape studies, but from meteorology.⁶

It would be interesting to hear of a musicology that does not talk in metaphors of high and low pitch or durations, of base notes and beats, of measures and division but instead uses metaphors, say, of turbulences and streams, of clouds and swarms, of temperature and humidity etc.⁷ Some already do so, especially in the French tradition, where they find ample material in the works and the aesthetic interests of Debussy, Messiaen, Grisey and Murail, but also in computer music, where swarm and turbulence modeling, pitch clouds and timbral fluctuations are all the rage. Yet most musicology still prefers to treat the scores and/or transcribed recordings as the basic landscape of music thinking – and musical interpretations and improvisations as ephemeral epiphenomena, as cloud shadows passing over these platonic landscapes. But, as Ingold asserts, weather (and possibly music, too) is not something we perceive as itself, it is not an object that interposes itself between us and the world – it is a medium: we perceive through it.

Let us continue to drift in this stream of thought for a moment. If music, the music we hear performed and the music we make by listening, is primarily a medium – what are the messages it transports? Most justifications of musicking as a human activity worthy of serious philosophical, political, and, crucially, economic attention heavily lean on the messages that music transports and the work that it does so well – namely to deliver these messages directly into our so-called 'hearts and minds.' So, what are these messages then? I believe they come in two varieties: coded and uncoded messages.

Coded messages are all those messages that would usually be seen as cultural 'content': emotions, repetitions, politics, drama, bliss, numerology, advice, humor, etc. They all rely on a code/key system shared by music makers and listeners; Indian musicology would call it the Rasa/Bhava system of artistic meaning. Music makers tend to code the musical stream, intentionally or by habit – and this affordance, the possibility to send coded messages from one set of music makers to practically unlimited listeners is often the core motive why people make a particular kind of music, why singers make up a song or composers compose a score. They often do this "creative work" in a pre-formed cultural or traditional code: the

6. Tim Ingold, *Being Alive. Essays on Movement, Knowledge and Description*, Routledge, New York 2011, p.138.

7. John Durham Peters, in his book *The Marvelous Clouds. Towards a Philosophy of Elemental Media* (University of Chicago Press, Chicago 2014) describes how the emphasis on aesthetic objects instead of atmospheres and elemental contexts is often accompanied by misogynistic discourses or practices. An "elemental musicology" might thus also offer a better chance at a more gender-inclusive perspective on human musicking.

primary function of these codes is to lighten the burden of thinking – and to make communication possible.

Another approach, one that was often taken in post-WWII ‘avantgarde’ music, is to invest their creativity at another nexus: to invent new codes which one would then like one’s listeners to learn – a kind of meta-coding, a kind of “private esperantoes” as Hamza Walker once called them.⁸ In the case of avantgarde music, the code itself becomes a message: you humble listener, you have much to learn before my music can even begin to offer you its grace. Similar to rites of passage in many cultures, the performance of aesthetic exclusivity at times became more important to avantgarde music circles than the music that was actually performed.

Many talks and discussions in this conference, I am sure, will address the potential, power, and pleasure of coded messaging and/or of messages coded through music – just as the bulk of historical and current theorizing about music has done for many millennia now, across all musical cultures. After all, most of us want to know what other human beings have to say... at least those whose codes we share.

But what about those uncoded messages? Do they exist? What are they like? And what do they say? When a medium, along with its main transmission, sends uncoded messages, then these undercover messages could offer an answer to the tricky question of why people choose this particular medium of music to send their coded messages to others. After all, why do we need music to communicate with other human beings if there are so many other ways to do this?

Also: a message that has not been culturally coded and yet appears significant must talk to us as human beings beyond cultural/traditional conventionality. It must enact its meaning in some way that affects every human being. It must embody something universal, or at least uni-human – we cannot speak for all lifeforms after all.⁹

V

All thinking about universals in music (or any cultural expression) is burdened with colonial and culturalist world stories: each historical power centre once imagined its way of life, and therefore also its music, to be of universal significance. Dominant systems always think big of themselves – in parallel to Fred Moten’s and Stefano Harney’s concept of the

8. In a panel discussion at the Transonic Festival at the HKW Berlin, January 2003.

9. Cf. Donna Haraway’s insistence on thinking our lives as intertwined with those of other species – which in a not-so-distant future may include non-biological intelligences. She explains her concept of “Chthulucene,” not to be confused with *Cthulhu* from H.P. Lovecraft’s fiction, as follows: “Chthulucene is a simple word. It is a compound of two Greek roots (khthôn and kainos) that together name a kind of timeplace for learning to stay with the trouble of living and dying in response-ability on a damaged earth” (Donna Haraway, *Staying with the Trouble. Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Durham 2016, p. 2).

“Undercommons,”¹⁰ I have called this attitude “overcommons” thinking.¹¹ Overcommons thinking is characterized by hyperbole: nothing less than universality will satisfy its aesthetic expansionism. Thus, a militarily and economically dominant society often feels the urge to position its own art making as universal, and the music of others as just so much local – and thus insignificant – noise. Postcolonial thinking has deconstructed most of the cultural stratagems and moves whereby and wherefore this urge is enacted. All talk about cultural universals is now widely understood to be nothing more than a power grab.

But music as a praxis has remained curiously resistant to this deconstruction. We all accept now that each musical tradition is a highly coded language that relies on initiation and/or intense study and/or lifelong emic familiarity to be appreciated, to evoke conventional emotions.

I was born in India, have lived in “the West” since I was five, and have trained in eurological music. Even with a childhood in and many long visits to India, with a lifelong interest in Hindustani music, even after closely working with Hindustani art musicians for over 30 years, my emotional reactions to a raag are still not intuitive. In the ensemble I founded in Pune, the *Ensemble Sangeet Prayog*, we explicitly make experimental music together, expanding concepts and practices from Indian musicking into new forms, practices, and concepts. And after all this exposure to and knowledge of the raag system, I am still baffled when the musicians there immediately agree on the emotion range and the raag of a random, seemingly a-tonal sequence of notes that my computer software just came up with – and by the realization how different that emotion range they describe is from the one I feel rise in me, conditioned as I am by years of listening to Webern, Schönberg, and their melodic tradition.

Yet, at the same time, we notice that all musicking has the potential to speak to “etic” listeners directly and emotionally without explanation. The emotions may not be the same as those of initiated listeners, but emotions they are – and they seem to generate genuine attachment to a music whose context and conventions the listener really knows nothing about. The entire music industry, and especially its world music part, rests on this simple fact – as does another received wisdom about music, namely that music transcends boundaries. This is mysterious – and would again suggest that there are things in music that have nothing to do with its cultural codes. That there are either uncoded messages that transport listeners – whether they actually know it or not. Or that music is indeed like the weather – it holds us in its immersive grip, whether we pay attention to it or not.

10. A distributed social layer of activists, artists and academics that provides the educational resources for necessary structural societal change with regard to black living – see: Stefano Harney & Fred Moten, *The Undercommons: Fugitive Planning & Black Study*, Wivenhoe/New York 2013, <https://www.minorcompositions.info/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/undercommons-web.pdf>.

11. Cf. my essay “New Music: Towards a Diversity of Practices” in the journal *On Curating*, Issue 47 (September 2020), <https://www.on-curating.org/issue-47-reader/new-music-towards-a-diversity-of-practices.html#.Ydv7SP7MIVA>.

VI

How musical is living? This is the question I ask in the title, and it is clear that any answer to this question must come from the non-aesthetic, non-tradition-specific, non-intentional, in short: from those uncoded messages within the musical experience which many composers since John Cage have sought to make accessible within cultural settings – and a performance like the one by *Ensemble Extrakte* that I described at the outset would be impossible to imagine without this belief that the messages of music can manifest themselves also in a non-culture-specific way, in non-intentional events and co-incidences. Just like in living, musicking always comes with an agenda, but it is very clear that the ostensible agenda only slightly determines what actually happens – and what it all means to us. Maybe, again, this is because music is not something we can encounter as a distanced spectator, neither as an object nor as a performance, but because it is something that we are always immersed in. In one of his essays in his book “Weltfremdheit,” Peter Sloterdijk asks a simple question: “Where are we when we listen to music?” He elaborates:

The seeing subject stands “at the rim” of the world as a world- and bodyless eye in front of a panorama ... However, ... it is in the nature of hearing that it never happens otherwise than in the mode of Being-within-Sound. No listener can believe that s/he stands at the margin of the audible.

The ear does not know any vis-à-vis, it does not develop a frontal “view” on distant things, for it has “world” and “things” only to the degree that it is in midst of an acoustic event – or to put it differently, insofar as it levitates or is immersed in auditive space.... Immersive behaviour often is revealed not by an active interest in everything that surrounds a subject, but by introversion of the subjects unto themselves...

Where are we, thus, when we listen to music? The location must remain vague – but it is certain that we cannot wholly be in the world. For hearing in a musical sense always means: to go towards the world or to flee it...¹²

Living and musicking thus exist in a complex dance of mutual immersiveness – sometimes living is immersed in musicking and sometimes musicking is immersed in living.

The terms that this symposium has put up for debate and reflection provoke questions about the worldliness of music. They seem to ask: If we indeed go towards the world while listening – how and when do we do this?

From a narrow perspective these terms could be read as questions about the performative, engaged, knowledge-producing relationship of some people making or listening to music to other people making or listening to music. They would therefore concern only what I called the coded messages of music.

12. Peter Sloterdijk, in: *Weltfremdheit*, Suhrkamp Verlag, Frankfurt a.M. 1993 (Translation by the present author).

But in the final sections of my talk, I would like to point to another reading of these terms, one that leads us away from the focus on coded messaging through music – and may perhaps offer a different perspective on what it means to perform, to engage or to know with music – namely, how it may help us, as Sloterdijk would say, to flee beyond the narrow window on the world that our individual perception limits us to.

VII

One of the most elusive realities of the non-human world is its abundant variety of timescales. From the SUMMIT supercomputer with 200 petaflops to the 4.5 billion years half-life of Uranium-238, the temporalities of interaction within our natural and artificial *umwelt* do not easily map onto the speed of chemical reactions that determine human perceptions and actions: We struggle to consciously experience the less than 100 years of our individual life, and everything that requires cognitive reaction times of less than 1 second must be done reflexively.

Dwarfed by these 30 orders of magnitude of our *umwelt*,¹³ how can we, who from cradle to grave live within only 10 orders of magnitude and whose aesthetic senses perceive only 2-3 orders of temporal magnitude, hope to understand, feel and react to the temporal reality of our interactions with this planet? Especially, when the many fast decisions we must make every day tend to have extremely long-lasting effects? When these effects of our decisions are so gradual that our guts feel nothing about them?

Eco-philosopher David Wood, in his book *Deep Time, Dark Times. On Being Geologically Human*,¹⁴ observes how attunement and the passions “play an indispensable role of binding us to the cosmos, reminding us of what matters, as well as impeding our response to the challenges that face us.” Attunement is probably what Sloterdijk had in mind when he noticed our immersive reaction to music, our Being-Within-Sound. We almost instantaneously attune ourselves to the weather – and to music. Instantaneity is a property of the world that we have only recently started to call “real time” – every time I hear it, I want to ask how real this time can be when our measure for it is our own perception of seamless movement – which can be tricked so easily that all our moving image technologies and our digital recording technologies depend on this deception. In other words, from all the abundant variety of timescales, we usually only find reality in one – the one that is at the same scale as our perception.

13. An “order of magnitude” is used here in the mathematical sense as an exponential power relation. A factor of 102 (=100) is one order of magnitude less than a factor 103 (=1000). The ten orders of magnitude we live in can be calculated thus: the smallest humanly perceivable time difference 25ms multiplied by a factor of 1010 (= 10 billion) gives us about 76 years, i.e. an average human lifespan. From shortest separately perceivable musical tone at about 100ms to the slowest musically useful tempo (say, about 2 bpm which consists of 30-second-long pulses) there are thus just 2.3 orders of magnitude in musical time – you may stretch that a bit, but not much...

14. David Wood, *Deep Time, Dark Times. On Being Geologically Human*, Fordham UP, New York 2019.

Wood, as have others before him, attributes our understanding of worldliness and reality to our passionate engagement with the cosmos: those passions tell us what we should engage with, and how we should act. And he points out that precisely the same attunement and passions are the factors that prevent us from engaging with our planet in a productive manner, of reacting effectively to crises that do not fit into our concept of “real time.”

Our quicksilver preference for short-term emotional resonance translates into an emotional nonchalance vis-à-vis slow-moving (i.e. “boring”) evolutions: the very volatility of our aesthetic sense that lets us successfully connect to other people and enjoy fast-moving music also prevents us from emotionally connecting to the long-term processes that may destroy our habitat and its people. The widespread understanding of music as an expression of emotions, as a mirror of our passions, seems thus make a lot of musicking a co-agent in the anthropogenic decomposition of our human habitat.

So, what could musicking be in the shadow of the Anthropocene? How could music, too, become “geologically human,” as David Wood asks us to? Must we learn to relish boring music? Must we abandon our passion for the passionate?

VIII

I propose two complementary approaches, both grounded in older traditions of musicking than those practices that have built and occupied the concert stages of this planet over the last two hundred years. The first approach is what I have called the Anti-Kairos.¹⁵ And the second, informed by Salomé Voegelin’s analysis of sonic fictionality,¹⁶ by the ecological “echopraxia” pursued by Frances Dyson¹⁷ and by the concept of inter-generational turn-taking formulated by Matthias Fritsch¹⁸ could be called a continuum approach, one that rethinks the concept of the traditional.

Kairos is the old Greek philosophical term for fortuitous conjunctures of fate, for the bliss of experiencing the simultaneous culmination of two different time streams. *Kairos* moments are, by necessity, rare, and as such have attracted a symbolic importance: A moment of *kairos*, such as a simultaneous orgasm between lovers, or the right moment to tip a complex process (or a football) towards a goal has for a long time been regarded as something that is not only exceptional, but also somehow significant, gratifying, and therefore important to aim for. In music, for example, an important aspect of expressivity is built upon the fact that two or more sonic streams culminate in a specific moment – all counterpoint, be it melodic

15. Cf. my essay “Anti-Kairos oder: Vom Aushalten des Ungleichzeitigen”, in: *Positionen. Texte zur aktuellen Musik*, No. 123, May 2020.

16. Salomé Voegelin, *Sonic Possible Worlds. Hearing the Continuum of Sound*, Bloomsbury, London 2014.

17. Frances Dyson, *The Tone of our Times. Sound, Sense, Economy and Ecology*, MIT Press, Cambridge MA, 2014.

18. Matthias Fritsch, *Taking Turns With the Earth. Phenomenology, Deconstruction and Intergenerational Justice*, Stanford UP, 2016.

(like e.g. in European *prima prattica*) or rhythmical (like in Hindustani *jugalbandi*) or timbral/social (as in Inuit *katajjaq*) is predicated on creating excitement, bliss, relief through the anticipation, annunciation and “salvation” through simultaneity.¹⁹

The entire concept of tonal harmony with its cadential tensions rests on the significance of *kairos*, i.e. the right pitches at the right moment, just as the Korean *changdan* rhythm cycles which swing from emptiness to fullness at just the right moment. In fact, a lot of music, especially learned music, consists of strategies to manage and manufacture *kairos* moments. Listeners and habitués to these music traditions are hooked on intense *kairos*-dependencies: passion-based music listening is one that expects quasi-orgasmic events in rather quick and relentless succession.

But, as Wood observes, this search for *kairos* moments, for attunement to and the belief in the significance of simultaneous events makes us blind and dumb for the real temporal phenomena that govern our existence – phenomena that are not dependent on simultaneity to do their work: geological, biological, astronomical processes happen not only at speeds we are not trained to process, they also appear boring to use precisely because they only rarely result in *kairos* moments. It seems telling that of all the temporal evolutions that presage the end of our current world, we again are most gripped by their *kairos* expressions: storms, floods, heat waves. We thus pay more attention to accidental conjunctures of those processes than to the individual processes by themselves.

Musicking the Anthropocene might perhaps just mean that we need to look for other temporality behaviors and frameworks than those on offer in many current musical practices. Maybe the craving for simultaneity is one of the aspects of the Hindu and Buddhist concept of *maya*, the veil of illusion that prevents us from experiencing temporal reality.

But do musics actually exist in which simultaneity is not a main concern of music making and listening? Where *kairos* moments are not more than a passing happenstance, to be noticed – or to just be left alone? Where significance resides in clouds rather than in points, in processes rather than in culminations, in fluxes rather than in cruxes?

Yes, of course, they exist in many music traditions – from silk-and-bamboo music in Ming China to the *alaapanas*, *pallavi niravals* and *tani avartanams* of Carnatic music, from many indigenous collective traditions such as the Aka and Banda Linda polyphonies in Central Africa to the Ami polyphonies in Taiwan. They all do not only flow in what Martin Scherzinger calls “elastic” time, but also do not overly emphasize the moments of *kairos* that occur in them.

Even in eurolgical concert music, such passages can be found – in the works of Iannis Xenakis and mid-career György Ligeti (although these composers mostly employ such moments of “confusion” to make a subsequent *kairos* moment even more savory and

19. Even without religious overtones, Carl Gustav Jung’s examination of the psychological role of synchronicity points to the same exaggerated trust in the significance of simultaneous occurrences.

dramatic), in the works of Eliane Radigue, Pauline Oliveros,²⁰ and Jin Hi Kim – and more explicitly as a musical strategy for the Anthropocene they become a focus in the music projects of Charles Ives and, lately, John Luther Adams. Adams' "songbirdsongs," his "Inuksuit" for 100 percussionists and especially his permanent installation "The Place Where You Go to Listen"²¹ are manifestations of temporal processes that unfold beyond the constraints of human temporalities and leave the sweetness of simultaneity behind, seeking another kind of musical beauty.

Such beauty also, surprisingly, can be found in eurological classical music. Its composers have known for a long time: When composing complex counterpoint forms such as fugues, tiny variances at the beginning will have major consequences for the flow of the music later on. Such consequences travel at vastly different speeds, yet constantly interact with each other in co-dependent and co-generative ways, taking turns in leading and determining the harmonic and rhythmic climate of the moment. In such complex, multilayered music forms, both quicksilver passions and slow-moving temporalities seem to co-exist and actually enhance each other.

Listeners in the eurological classical tradition have learnt how to patiently listen to – and feel – such complex temporalities in music. Could we temporally challenged humans – instead of reading time-invariant, distancing visual curves, tables, and texts – also learn to inhabit the temporalities of climate change by learning how make them audible, and to learn how to feel and listen to them – as a complex flux of polyphonic processes?

IX

In the flurry of daily happenings, in the internet-powered illusion of instantaneity that Paul Virilio²² once called the globalization (and thus mainstreaming) of history and time,²³ we thus lose not only our mental and geological perspective, we also lose our perspective on the temporal interdependencies in which we are immersed at this very moment. Musicking – as we know it so far – more often than not abstracts us from our environment by

20. A performance of Oliveros' music at the New Tate Turbine Hall is memorably described as "swarming tones and tonalities, materials and materialities, merged not as one but into the complexity of a heterogenous work...individual bits, oddments, sticking out here and there ... to be brought back into the commingling of sounds as the shape of the work's formless flow...a form forming in the time of its performance" (in: Voegelin 2014, p.78).

21. John Luther Adams, *The Place Where You Go to Listen: In Search of an Ecology of Music*, Wesleyan UP, Middletown CT, 2009.

22. Paul Virilio, *The Information Bomb*, Verso Books, London 1999, p. 8.

23. The mainstreaming of time is a further problematic nuance of our current temporal behaviour, one with strong colonialist overtones: just as eurological music during the small ice age between 1500 and 1800 slowly shifted from polyphonic and thus poly-temporal musics to a type of monophonic and mono-temporal music which subsumed polyphony into harmony, our perception of temporalities between different areas of the globe has equally shifted from a clear understanding that societal time may move differently in different regions of the planet to our present sense that our time is essentially the same – and if it palpably is not, the differences in its behaviour are often seen as marginal and inconsequential rather than as structural and revelatory.

embedding us in a bubble of self-referential resonances where the only time we know of is the one we feel.

Thus, Frances Dyson asks us to move “past the association of sound with interiority and self-awareness.” In her plea for a new “echopraxia” she argues that

whereas echo always introduces the environment (ecology), resonance can be an internal operation that also flows, logically almost, into culture; whereas echo is bound to death and earth, resonance multiplies with the promise of the immaterial and immortal.²⁴

Sounds (and the musics made from them) cannot remain resonances within the cultural sphere, they cannot just be instances of a timeless code. She hears them echo within and off the multiplicity of processes in our human and terrestrial environments.

Converging from a different trajectory, Salomé Voegelin details how we must abandon our self-centered engagement with sound by realizing that we are constantly creating what she calls “sonic fictions”:

From invisible pigeons to murmurs of water, from the sound of distorting voices to deep woods and sonic threads, we walk, centering, decentering, and recentering ourselves through alternative intuitions that produce variants of the same world and show us slices of which it is made.

In these alternative intuitions, she

hears the invisible mobility of sound connecting, disconnecting, and reconnecting things that we believe to see in stillness...The movement within and across works as worlds... and the compossibility of works, not as logical and abstract but as concrete and lived worlds through which we move in listening... grants us access to the fissures and the continuum between works.²⁵

Voegelin’s description of the different variants of the world which (and to which) we can connect, disconnect, and reconnect through sound rings, to my ears at least, like a recipe for listening to the various different temporalities that traverse the environment around us. She exhorts us to make the connections ourselves, and thereby indeed abandon our implicit need for the inner-musical theatre of passions, fueled by our craving for *kairos*. It is an engagement for music and sound that does not put us and our temporality-challenged perception at the centre of things. It allows for active *per-form-ance*, i.e. the making of forms by a process of centering, decentering and recentering, thus creating a sonic fiction, “a form forming in the time of its performance.”²⁶

24. Dyson 2014, p. 153.

25. Voegelin 2014, p. 82.

26. Voegelin 2014, p. 78.

X

Back to last weekend's performance by *Ensemble Extrakte* in the Martin-Gropius-Bau, the piece entitled "...how to inhabit these different temporalities...". True to the title, each musician had their own mechanical metronome, its tempo was assigned to them by members of the public who placed postcards before them on which one could read the tempo and a poem describing the mood of their performance. No one could know in advance how fast they would be asked to perform the score in front of them. Even less could they practice how this score would fit into the flow of the music around them. Yet their main instruction was to listen to the music and metronome streams of the other musicians, to the talking and the movements of the audience in the room – and to somehow connect their tempo and their playing to the existing time-flows.

In Voegelin's words, they were invited to create a sonic fiction out of disparate temporal elements, each of which was beyond the control or even the purposeful agency of anyone in particular. No musician knew when, how, or at which location they would be asked to play with whom. Although most of them are expert improvisers, albeit in different idiomatic improvising traditions, they could also not improvise freely: that would have quickly led them down the path to *kairos*-driven music. Instead, they needed to keep the balance between the time and spatial relationship to the others that they were thrown into, the histories and landscapes of their own scores, and their own ability to make connections to these other moving and living musical entities, who sounded in the same room, but did not share the same sonic fiction with them.

Over three days, 8 hours a day, they all upheld this iridescent braid of musical fluxes. And they did so to their increasing musicking delight, as well as to the listening delight of many audience members, many who serendipitously encountered this room in their parcours of a larger exhibition – and who then often spent more than an hour immersed in its sonic weather.

The title of the exhibition was "Down To Earth," after Bruno Latour's eponymous book.²⁷ Its aim was to explore "how the agenda of a shift in climate policy affects our own 'operating system.' How can we sustainably change the mode in which we work, eat, travel or make exhibitions?" One of the constraints of the exhibition was that electricity was banned in the exhibition spaces, which for musicians meant: no amplification. One of the challenges of the artistic process was to orchestrate the performance setting in such a way that loud and less loud instruments did not mask each other, that they all would become audible. Surprisingly that task turned out to be not that difficult – our problem with acoustic inequality and different loudnesses, for the most part, seems to be a problem created by simultaneity and forced coherence. In this setting, with each musician inhabiting their own, different temporality, even soft-voiced instruments (one consisting only of water drops on a stretched balloon skin) had a fair chance of being heard. Clocks are instruments, and synchronization

27. Bruno Latour, *Down to Earth. Politics in the New Climatic Regime*, Polity Press, Cambridge, UK 2018.

seems to be as much a power grab as a universal tuning frequency would be – both are expressions of an arbitrary centralized time regime, abstracted at an ever-growing distance from the rhythms of the earth.

XI

Echopraxia, according to Dyson, is a sound praxis entangled with mortality and the earth. In his seminal book “Taking Turns with the Earth,” Matthias Fritsch memorably defines earth as that which not only “claims the corpse,” a thought inherent in many cultural practices around dying, but that which also therefore “claims the living body.” He writes:

...earth names the mortal condition of life... As habitat and natural history, then, earth may name that which absorbs and claims the body...

Death is inscribed in life, and therefore life, in Fritsch’s words is forced

to be always already turned to its context of its inscription without the possibility of a return... Western individualism and imperialism... responds to its fear of death by seeking to master the ... earth and animals.

Fritsch, much as Haraway, Dyson and Voegelin sees a “deprivileging of *the* human” as one of the most urgent solutions to the crises that threaten to erase our presence from the face of the earth. He explains:

What should be of further note here is that this deprivileging of *the* human goes along with a deprivileging of the present, the time of the living and sovereign present, as if our time was owned by our generation.²⁸

From this Fritsch develops his ethics of turn-taking: to him ethics suffers crucially from what he calls presentism – only those now living are deemed to be worthy of ethical considerations. He proposes an ethical framework that includes “the generations of the dead and the unborn” which he, moreover, does not consider to be “exclusively and exceptionally human.” An understanding of life that considers our presence here to be our turn at inhabiting the world’s time streams.

This idea of passing on what one has to future generations is in itself not alien to human societies – but in contemporary discourse it is associated with aristocratic or, at the other end of the power spectrum, indigenous overtones – both of which have very little clout in our current majoritarian political systems and their short-term dynamics that privilege *kairos*, passion, and the so-called “human angle.” As it is usually understood, the concept of the caretaker is also anthropocentric, in that it appoints humans to be the guardians of the planet – a task at which our current performance as a species seems to be rather substandard.

28. Fritsch 2018, p. 198.

Fritsch transforms the anthropocentric concept of us as the “caretakers” of earth into an understanding of humans as “turn-takers”: we, as all others who currently live in this terrestrial ecology, can only be seen as those whose turn it happens to be – a privilege with an inscribed handover fate.

I had been wondering for some time how Fritsch’s intergenerational ethics could be transposed into intergenerational aesthetics. Until I realized that another term that has lost relevance and energy in current aesthetic discourse, a concept used mostly defensively and in fervent appeals to conservationism, could actually be the concept that could express and guide us through many of the issues this text has touched upon: namely, the concept of tradition.

Modernity discourses have often portrayed traditions as static and concerned with the past. As most of you know, nothing could be further from reality: Traditions do not really care about the past *as the past*, they use those parts of it that can be relevant to their own time and ignore the rest. Every tradition works like an antiques shop: keep and sell the good things, using the latest ideas and technologies – and lose the dross.

As such, a music tradition is a perfect example of a taking of turns. It survives on a turn-taker-ethics that requires each musician in a traditional context to be aware 1) that the aesthetic context they perform in did not originate in their time 2) that they must therefore mold it into something that is of their own time 3) that, in the process, and however much they talk about of preserving the past, they must reinvent their tradition so that 4) future music makers in their tradition have a chance to do the same.²⁹

Conceiving musicking thus in terms of a re-thought traditionality that would incorporate Dyson’s echopraxia, Voegelin’s sonic fictionality (is not every tradition a sonic fiction of the past?), and Fritsch’s problematization of presentism would not only once more open up musical thinking to the world around us, but would also add new orders of magnitude to our understanding of musical time. Such a re-imagining of traditions could be one seed for an aesthetic project that could indeed musick the geological – a musicking that would be open to the many different temporalities of the real world around us, and that would help us inhabit them in a responsive and engaged manner.

A musical idea intoned in the twelfth century can then still be known, be relevant and heard to be sounding today, evolving through generations of turn-takers molding it into ever new forms that per-form the times they traverse. Different streams of such turn-taking musical ideas and practices could flow together in trans-traditional laminar and turbulent

29. At this point, I would like to assert here, as I have elsewhere, that new/avantgarde/contemporary eurological music, however anti-traditional it may portray itself, is emphatically also a type of traditional music – albeit a young and still neurotic one. Not only does it rely heavily on musicians trained in older traditions, in its evolution it itself has by now followed all of the steps above, has completed the full cycle from branching off from a strong tradition into becoming one itself, one from which new branches can and do now sprout.

polyphonies, weaving in and out of *kairos*, in and out of coherence without losing cohesion – just as the processes do that *per-form* our planet. A trans-human project of musicking could be seen to be underway in which musicking is not only an exercise in introspection but also one in circumspection. And amid the multiple courses of its times, we then may, with some reasonable hope for a helpful answer, ask how musical our living really is: how our lives, lived beyond all soundtracks and playlists, can themselves be mutually listened to in a kind of temporal polyphony.

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Note: This contribution was presented as a keynote address for the at the 7th Study Group Meeting of the ICTM Study Group on Applied Ethnomusicology, which was titled “Performing, Engaging, Knowing.” The paper submitted to the meeting was revised for this publication.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7273918